

Thermal Dynamic Models for Predicting the Indoor Temperature of Multi-Zone Buildings

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Abstract—Reducing the energy consumption of buildings is vital for achieving the European Union’s climate targets. Towards this direction, one important strategy is to intelligently manage the indoor temperature of buildings to minimize energy consumption without compromising the comfort levels of residents. This can be accomplished through model predictive control frameworks that utilize low-complexity thermal dynamic models tailored to the building and heating/cooling system characteristics. This work builds on a single-zone first-order resistance-capacitance (RC) model to develop a *multi-zone IRIC model* for the prediction of indoor temperatures in multi-zone buildings. To enhance the prediction accuracy of the derived model, a *bimodal multi-zone IRIC model* is further proposed that handles separately the *on* and *off* states of the heating system. An estimation framework is then developed based on the least square method to estimate the parameters of the two models using datasets obtained from the EnergyPlus simulator and historical weather data. Simulation results showcase the capability of the proposed models to accurately predict the temperatures of the different zones. The results also demonstrate the superiority of the *bimodal multi-zone IRIC model* in terms of prediction accuracy compared to the *multi-zone IRIC model*.

Index Terms—Estimation framework, multi-zone buildings, temperature prediction, thermal dynamic RC models.

I. INTRODUCTION

The buildings sector accounted for 34% of global energy demand in 2022 with electricity use covering 35% of the total energy demand [1]. Specifically, 30% of the total energy demand was allocated for heating and cooling purposes. According to the global status report for buildings and construction [1], the reduction of the electricity consumption of heating and cooling systems in buildings is vital for achieving the targets of reducing CO₂ emissions by 50% by 2030, while ensuring the indoor temperature remains comfortable for occupants. To achieve this target, accurate mathematical models for predicting the indoor temperatures of multi-zone buildings based on their heating/cooling electricity consumption must be developed. These models can be integrated into model predictive control (MPC) approaches to manage the temperature of buildings and energy consumption of heating/cooling systems.

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Mathematical models for forecasting the indoor building temperature can be categorized as *white-box*, *black-box*, and *grey-box* based on their complexity and accuracy. White-box models, utilized in EnergyPlus [2] and TRNSYS [3] simulators, use complex physics equations of the buildings, yielding accurate predictions of the temperature. However, white-box models require knowledge of buildings’ characteristics which may be unavailable or challenging to be collected accurately [4]. Black-box models use machine learning methods, e.g., neural networks, to predict the building temperature by obtaining statistical patterns from data [5]. Although black-box models are independent of complex mathematical equations of buildings, they require high-quality data and a large number of model parameters to yield accurate forecasts.

Grey-box models use properties from both black-box and white-box models, such as machine learning techniques, measured data, and partial system knowledge to predict the indoor temperature of buildings. To consider the system knowledge in grey-box approaches, thermal resistance-capacitance (RC) models of different orders are widely used to simplify heat transfer dynamics [6], providing a trade-off between prediction accuracy and complexity. A three-resistance two-capacitance (3R2C) thermal model is proposed in [7] for estimating the indoor temperature of a single-zone building. Similarly, a 2R2C model is presented in [8] for estimating the aggregate temperature of a building with different zones. In [9], a higher order 4R3C model is developed and integrated into an MPC framework for predicting the indoor temperature of a single-zone building by controlling its heating energy consumption. All high-order models developed in [7]–[9] focus on predicting the aggregated indoor temperature of multi-zone or single-zone buildings; however, they do not consider each zone individually to ensure a desirable comfort level in each room.

A multi-zone high-order RC model is proposed in [10] to predict the indoor temperature of each zone in multi-zone buildings. This model is also integrated into an MPC framework to minimize the electricity cost of a heating ventilation air conditioning (HVAC) system by controlling its air mass flow, ensuring the temperature limits in each zone. In [11], a multi-zone high-order RC thermal model is incorporated into an MPC optimization scheme to minimize the energy consumption of a heat pump’s ventilation system by controlling its air mass flow rate. Similarly, an MPC strategy

integrating a single-zone RC thermal model is developed in [12] to minimize the operating cost of an HVAC system by controlling its air handling units (AHUs), while ensuring the occupant's comfort level. Although the high-order single-zone or multi-zone RC models presented in [7]–[12] enhance forecasting accuracy, they require additional characteristics and measurements from buildings [13], e.g., the capacity and average temperature of structure walls, which are often unavailable in practical applications.

Low-order 2R1C and 1R1C thermal models are proposed in [14] for predicting the indoor air temperature of a single-zone building. Although the 2R1C model yields more accurate results compared to 1R1C model, it requires additional sensors to capture the mean radiant temperature of surrounding surfaces perceived by occupants, including walls and other radiating and absorbing objects. A single-zone first-order RC model of an air-conditioned home is presented in [15]; however, this model does not consider the indoor temperature for multi-zone buildings. First-order 1R1C networks require minimal information from the building operation which is desirable for practical applications; however, these simplified models may deteriorate the prediction accuracy. Therefore, there is a need for a simplified multi-zone 1R1C thermal model, based on the single-zone 1R1C model, that can predict accurately the indoor temperature of multi-zone buildings based on their heating/cooling electricity consumption; such a model can be easily integrated into MPC formulations.

This work builds on a single-zone first-order 1R1C thermal model, which requires minimal information from the building operation, to develop a *multi-zone 1R1C model* for the prediction of the indoor temperatures in multi-zone buildings based on the environmental conditions and the energy consumption of their heating system. To enhance the prediction accuracy of the derived model, a *bimodal multi-zone 1R1C model* is proposed that considers individually the *on* and *off* states of the heating system. Moreover, an optimization scheme based on the least-squares method is developed to estimate the parameters of the derived models using a training dataset obtained from the EnergyPlus simulator and historical weather data. In summary, this work has the following main contributions:

- Development of a *multi-zone 1R1C model* for the prediction of the indoor temperatures in multi-zone buildings by modifying a single-zone 1R1C thermal model.
- Development of a *bimodal multi-zone 1R1C model* to enhance the prediction accuracy by considering individually the *on* and *off* states of the heating system.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II states the underlying problem and Section III describes the proposed thermal models and the estimation framework. Simulation results are presented in Section IV and conclusions are given in Section V.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

This section states the underlying problem by presenting (a) a literature-based single-zone 1R1C thermal model and (b)

Fig. 1. A representation of a single-zone building using an 1R1C thermal dynamic model, where T^I denotes the indoor air temperature, T^O the outdoor air temperature, Q^h the heating power system, and Q^s the global radiation.

Fig. 2. The derived multi-zone 1R1C thermal dynamic model based on the single-zone 1R1C, where an additional resistance ($R_{i,j}^N$) is added to capture the temperature interactions between zones i and j .

the derived multi-zone 1R1C thermal model that captures the indoor temperatures of different zones in multi-zone buildings.

A. Single-zone 1R1C model

This work considers low-order 1R1C thermal dynamic models because they can be easily integrated into MPC frameworks and require minimal information from building operations, making them suitable for practical applications. Towards this direction, we consider the single-zone 1R1C thermal model proposed in [7] and depicted Fig.1. As shown in Fig. 1, the 1R1C model captures building thermal dynamics using a network of temperature nodes, a thermal resistance, and a thermal capacitance. Considering the single-zone 1R1C model, the evolution of the indoor temperature, T^I , in response to various inputs such as the outdoor environmental temperature, T^O , heating power, Q^h , and global radiation, Q^s , is described through the differential equation

$$C \frac{dT^I}{dt} = \frac{1}{R} (T^O - T^I) + Q^h + Q^s, \quad (1)$$

where R , and C denote the model parameters. The derivative $\frac{dT^I}{dt}$ denotes the rate of change of the indoor temperature T^I with respect to time t . Parameters R and C denote the thermal resistance and capacitance of the 1R1C model, which are used to represent aggregate zone characteristics such as the surface heat resistance and zone thermal storage.

B. Multi-zone 1R1C model

To consider multi-zone buildings, we build on the single-zone 1R1C model to capture the indoor temperatures of

different zones by considering interactions between them. Let $\mathcal{I} = \{1, \dots, I\}$ denotes the building zones and $\mathcal{M}_i \in \mathcal{I}$ the set of all zones that are neighbours of the zone i . To consider the multiple zones, we introduce the thermal resistance elements $R_{i,j}^N$ to model the temperature interactions among neighboring zones $j \in \mathcal{M}_i, i \in \mathcal{I}$. Fig. 2 illustrates a graphical representation of a two-zone 1R1C model, where an additional resistance is added to capture the temperature interactions between zones i and j . Towards this direction, the differential equation in (1) is reformulated to consider each zone $i \in \mathcal{I}$ and capture the interactions between neighboring zones, given by

$$C_i \frac{dT_i^I}{dt} = \frac{1}{R_i} (T^O - T_i^I) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{M}_i} \frac{1}{R_{i,j}^N} (T_j^I - T_i^I) + \gamma_i Q_i^e + \delta_i Q_i^s, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \quad (2)$$

where T_i^I , Q_i^e , and Q_i^s denote the indoor temperature, electricity consumption of the heating system, and global radiation for each zone $i \in \mathcal{I}$; γ_i and δ_i denote the associated parameters of the electricity consumption of the heating system and global radiation; R_i denote the thermal resistance between the zone i and outdoor environment, where $1/R_i = 0$ when there is no direct contact of the zone i with the outdoor environment. In this work, we consider a radiant floor heating system and assume a linear relationship between the heating power Q_i^h and the electricity consumption of the heating system Q_i^e such that $Q_i^h \approx \gamma_i Q_i^e$; therefore, the Q_i^h is replaced with $\gamma_i Q_i^e$ in the derived model in (2). Parameter C_i denotes the thermal capacitance of zone $i \in \mathcal{I}$ which can be calculated as $C_i = \rho_i^a c_i^a V_i^a, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, where constants ρ_i^a denote the air density, c_i^a the heat capacity of air, and V_i^a the internal air volume for each zone $i \in \mathcal{I}$. Note that the model in (2) neglects the heating gains from human occupancy and equipment, which are often unavailable in practical applications.

The derived thermal model in (2) can be used to estimate the indoor temperature in multi-zone buildings considering as input measurements the electricity consumption of the heating system, environmental temperature, and global radiation. This work considers that the electricity consumption of the heating system can be measured by a smart meter installed in the heating system circuit, neglecting any potential noise in the measurements. However, the usage of this model requires the estimation of parameters $R_i, R_{i,j}^N, \gamma_i$, and $\delta_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, which are unknown or challenging to be accurately calculated in practical applications. In addition, the incorporation of the derived multi-zone 1R1C model in MPC frameworks is challenging because (2) is a differential equation. The aforementioned issues are addressed in the next section.

III. SOLUTION METHODOLOGY

This section discretizes the differential equation of the multi-zone 1R1C model using the Forward Euler method and develops an estimation framework to estimate the unknown parameters of the model. Moreover, a bimodal multi-zone 1R1C model is developed to enhance the prediction accuracy by considering the *on* and *off* states of the heating system.

A. Multi-zone 1R1C model

This work discretizes the differential equation in (2) utilizing the Forward Euler method that approximates the derivative $\frac{dT_i^I}{dt}$ using a forward difference, defined as

$$\frac{dT_i^I}{dt} \approx \frac{T_{i,k}^I - T_{i,k-1}^I}{\Delta t}, \quad (3)$$

where $T_{i,k}^I$ and $T_{i,k-1}^I$ denote the indoor temperature at time t_k and t_{k-1} , respectively, and $\Delta t = t_k - t_{k-1}$ is the time step. Replacing (3) in (2), the multi-zone 1R1C model is reformulated as,

$$T_{i,k}^I = \beta_i T_{i,k-1}^I + \frac{\Delta t}{C_i} \left[\frac{1}{R_i} (T_{k-1}^O - T_{i,k-1}^I) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{M}_i} \frac{1}{R_{i,j}^N} (T_{j,k-1}^I - T_{i,k-1}^I) + \gamma_i Q_{i,k-1}^e + \delta_i Q_{i,k-1}^s \right] + \epsilon_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, k \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathcal{K} = \{1, \dots, K\}$ denotes the considered time horizon. The auxiliary parameters β_i and ϵ_i are introduced to enhance the prediction accuracy of the model, where β_i provides a linear relationship between $T_{i,k}^I$ and $T_{i,k-1}^I$, and ϵ_i an offset correction. Considering the derived model in (4), an estimation framework is developed to estimate the unknown parameters $R_i, R_{i,j}^N, \beta_i, \gamma_i, \delta_i$, and $\epsilon_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}$. Towards this direction, an optimization problem based on the least-squares method is formulated to minimize the sum of the squares of the residuals, the difference between the estimated indoor temperature ($T_{i,k}^I$) obtained using model (4) and the observed (actual) indoor temperature ($\hat{T}_{i,k}^I$), defined as Problem \mathcal{P}^E

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize} \quad \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}^T} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (T_{i,k}^I - \hat{T}_{i,k}^I)^2, \\ & \text{s.t.} \quad T_{i,k}^I = \beta_i \hat{T}_{i,k-1}^I + \frac{\Delta t}{C_i} \left[\frac{1}{R_i} (\hat{T}_{k-1}^O - \hat{T}_{i,k-1}^I) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{M}_i} \frac{1}{R_{i,j}^N} (\hat{T}_{j,k-1}^I - \hat{T}_{i,k-1}^I) + \gamma_i \hat{Q}_{i,k-1}^e + \delta_i \hat{Q}_{i,k-1}^s \right] + \epsilon_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, k \in \mathcal{K}^T, \quad (5) \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathcal{K}^T = \{1, \dots, K^T\}$ denotes the considered time horizon of the training set. $T_{i,k}^I$ at time $k \in \mathcal{K}^T$, $R_i, R_{i,j}^N, \beta_i, \gamma_i, \delta_i$, and $\epsilon_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, denote the decision variables of Problem \mathcal{P}^E . Constants $\hat{T}_{i,k-1}^I, \hat{T}_{j,k-1}^I, \hat{T}_{k-1}^O, \hat{Q}_{i,k-1}^e$, and $\hat{Q}_{i,k-1}^s$ denote the actual values of the indoor temperature, outdoor temperature, electricity consumption of the radiant floor heating system, and global radiation at time $k-1$. Note that $\hat{Q}_{i,k-1}^e = 0$ when the heating is *off*; otherwise, $\hat{Q}_{i,k-1}^e > 0$. Problem \mathcal{P}^E is a convex quadratic program (QP) that can be fast and efficiently solved. Note that the derived model (4) with the estimated parameters $R_i, R_{i,j}^N, \beta_i, \gamma_i, \delta_i$, and $\epsilon_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, can be easily used in MPC-based frameworks using linear programming to manage the thermal energy of multi-zone buildings.

B. Bimodal multi-zone 1R1C model

Considering that the derived *multi-zone 1R1C* model in (4) is a non-ideal model which does not accurately capture the

TABLE I

BIMODAL MULTI-ZONE 1R1C MODEL: SELECTION OF PARAMETERS R_i , $R_{i,j}^N$, γ_i , δ_i , AND ϵ_i IN (4) BASED ON THE ON/OFF STATES OF THE HEATING SYSTEM AT TIME $k \in \mathcal{K}$.

Decision	Parameters
<i>on</i>	$R_i = R_i^{\text{on}}$, $R_{i,j}^N = R_{i,j}^{N,\text{on}}$, $\beta_i = \beta_i^{\text{on}}$, $\gamma_i = \gamma_i^{\text{on}}$, $\delta_i = \delta_i^{\text{on}}$, $\epsilon_i = \epsilon_i^{\text{on}}$
<i>off</i>	$R_i = R_i^{\text{off}}$, $R_{i,j}^N = R_{i,j}^{N,\text{off}}$, $\beta_i = \beta_i^{\text{off}}$, $\gamma_i = \gamma_i^{\text{off}}$, $\delta_i = \delta_i^{\text{off}}$, $\epsilon_i = \epsilon_i^{\text{off}}$

Algorithm 1 : Parameters estimation of the bimodal multi-zone 1R1C model

- 1: Define the sets $\mathcal{K}^{\text{on}} \in \mathcal{K}^T$ and $\mathcal{K}^{\text{off}} \in \mathcal{K}^T$.
- 2: Solve Problem \mathcal{P}^E using the set \mathcal{K}^{on} , instead of \mathcal{K}^T , to estimate the parameters R_i^{on} , $R_{i,j}^{N,\text{on}}$, β_i^{on} , γ_i^{on} , δ_i^{on} , and ϵ_i^{on} .
- 3: Solve Problem \mathcal{P}^E using the set \mathcal{K}^{off} to estimate the parameters R_i^{off} , $R_{i,j}^{N,\text{off}}$, β_i^{off} , γ_i^{off} , δ_i^{off} , and ϵ_i^{off} .

dynamics of the system, we consider the *on/off* states of the heating system independently to enhance its prediction accuracy. Towards this direction, we introduce the *bimodal multi-zone 1R1C model* that uses different parameters R_i , $R_{i,j}^N$, β_i , γ_i , δ_i , and ϵ_i , $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, in (4) based on the *on/off* states of the heating system at time $k \in \mathcal{K}$. Specifically, two separate training sessions are performed to estimate the parameters of the *on/off* states using data when the heating is *on* and *off*, respectively, achieving a better fit. The model parameters based on the *on/off* states of the heating system are presented in Table I and can be estimated using the proposed estimation framework presented in Section III-A.

Algorithm 1 summarizes the proposed procedure of estimating the parameters of the *bimodal multi-zone 1R1C model* using Problem \mathcal{P}^E . Initially, the training set \mathcal{K}^T is separated into the subsets $\mathcal{K}^{\text{on}} \in \mathcal{K}^T$ and $\mathcal{K}^{\text{off}} \in \mathcal{K}^T$ that include the time intervals where the heating system is *on* and *off*, respectively (Line 1). Next, Problem \mathcal{P}^E is solved to estimate the parameters R_i^{on} , $R_{i,j}^{N,\text{on}}$, β_i^{on} , γ_i^{on} , δ_i^{on} , and ϵ_i^{on} when the set \mathcal{K}^{on} is used instead of \mathcal{K}^T (Line 2). Finally, Problem \mathcal{P}^E is solved to estimate the parameters R_i^{off} , $R_{i,j}^{N,\text{off}}$, β_i^{off} , γ_i^{off} , δ_i^{off} , and ϵ_i^{off} when the set \mathcal{K}^{off} is considered (Line 3).

The proposed bimodal multi-zone 1R1C model, the derived model (4) with the estimated parameters in Table I, can be incorporated into MPC frameworks by introducing binary variables to indicate the *on/off* states of the heating system, resulting in mixed-integer programming (MIP) formulations.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section investigates the prediction accuracy of the proposed *multi-zone 1R1C model* and *bimodal multi-zone 1R1C model* using building data obtained from the EnergyPlus simulator and historical weather data. Moreover, the proposed models are compared with the *single-zone 1R1C model* proposed in [7], i.e., the model presented in (1). Specifically, the discretized *single-zone 1R1C model* can be obtained by ignoring the interaction between neighboring zones in model (4), setting $R_{i,j}^N = \infty$. The proposed models are also compared

with a high-order state-of-art *multi-zone 3R2C model*, which is derived by modifying the single-zone 3R2C thermal model proposed in [7] to consider multi-zone buildings, given by

$$T_{i,k}^I = \beta_i T_{i,k-1}^I + \frac{\Delta t}{C_i} \left[\frac{1}{R_i^S} (T_{k-1}^S - T_{i,k-1}^I) + \frac{1}{R_i^F} (T_{k-1}^O - T_{i,k-1}^I) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{M}_i} \frac{1}{R_{i,j}^N} (T_{j,k-1}^I - T_{i,k-1}^I) + \gamma_i Q_{i,k-1}^e + \delta_i Q_{i,k-1}^s \right] + \epsilon_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, k \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (6)$$

where $T_{i,k-1}^S$ denotes the average internal surface temperature of walls, doors, windows, floor, and roof at zone i and time $k-1$, which is associated with the thermal inertia of the building and heating system. R_i^I denotes the internal thermal resistance of zone i , and R_i^F the resistance that represents the thermal losses through windows and doors in zone i . Note that $1/R_i^F = 0$ when there is no direct contact of the zone i with the outdoor environment. The parameters R_i^I , R_i^F , $R_{i,j}^N$, β_i , γ_i , δ_i , and ϵ_i , $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, are estimated using the estimation framework proposed in Section III-A. In (6), we assume that the average surface temperature, $T_{i,k-1}^S$, is known for simplicity purposes (it is obtained from the EnergyPlus). Although the surface temperature can be predicted using a differential equation that associates the surface temperature with the surface thermal capacitance, i.e., the thermal inertia, it requires measurement data which are unknown in practical applications.

To examine the prediction accuracy of all thermal models, two performance metrics are considered: (a) the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), and (b) the Mean Absolute Error (MAE). The MAPE metric measures the average percentage difference between the actual indoor temperature, $\hat{T}_{i,k}^I$, and predicted indoor temperature, $T_{i,k}^I$, in % over the considered prediction horizon \mathcal{K} for each zone i , given by

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{|\hat{T}_{i,k}^I - T_{i,k}^I|}{\hat{T}_{i,k}^I} 100\%, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}. \quad (7)$$

The MAE metric measures the average absolute difference between the actual indoor temperature, $\hat{T}_{i,k}^I$, and predicted indoor temperature, $T_{i,k}^I$, in °C over the considered prediction horizon \mathcal{K} for each zone $i \in \mathcal{I}$, defined as

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K |\hat{T}_{i,k}^I - T_{i,k}^I|, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}. \quad (8)$$

Setup. The prediction accuracy of the proposed thermal models is evaluated using building data obtained from the EnergyPlus simulator and historical weather data obtained from [16] for the period from December 2004 to January 2005 in Nicosia, Cyprus. Specifically, the EnergyPlus simulator is used to build a four-zone building with well-insulated materials and a radiant floor heating system in each zone. Each zone is characterized by different structural dimensions and heating system design capacities. The weather data that involve the environmental temperature and global radiation, including direct normal radiation and diffuse horizontal radiation, are used as inputs in the simulator. Thus, the weather data do not

TABLE II
THE MAPE IN % FOR THE EVALUATION DAY 14/01/2005.

Models	Zone 1	Zone 2	Zone 3	Zone 4	Average
Multi-zone 1RIC	0.44%	0.32%	0.40%	0.67%	0.46%
Bimodal 1RIC	0.16%	0.15%	0.17%	0.38%	0.21%

TABLE III
THE MAE IN °C FOR THE EVALUATION DAY 14/01/2005.

Models	Zone 1	Zone 2	Zone 3	Zone 4	Average
Multi-zone 1RIC	0.10	0.07	0.09	0.15	0.10
Bimodal 1RIC	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.08	0.05

affect the validation process. The desirable temperature set-point for Zones 1, 2, and 3 is set to 22°C with lower and upper limits of 20.95°C and 23.05°C, while for Zone 4 is set to an eco mode of 21.5°C with limits of 19.9°C and 23.1°C. The EnergyPlus simulator produces the training sets that are used to estimate the parameters of the two models as well as the testing sets that are used to evaluate their performance. The internal thermal capacitance $C_i = \rho_i^a c_i^a V_i^a$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, is calculated considering (a) an air density of $\rho_i^a = 1.192$ ($\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$) in all zones at a standard room temperature of 23°C, (b) a heat air capacity of $c_i^a = 700$ ($\frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg}^\circ\text{C}}$) in all zones, and (c) an internal air volume of $V_i^a = \{191.82, 63.82, 204.26, 150.62\}$ (m^3) in each zone of the four-zone building. In this work, we assume a constant air density for simplicity purposes, i.e., enabling the formulation of linear programs, because it presents a small variation from 1.2 to 1.192 ($\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$) for a fluctuation of the indoor temperature from 21°C to 23°C. The proposed thermal models are coded in Matlab and Problem \mathcal{P}^E is solved using optimization solver Gurobi [17] on a personal computer with 8 GB RAM and an Intel Core-i5 3.2 GHz processor.

Performance Evaluation. The prediction accuracy of the proposed *multi-zone 1RIC model* and *bimodal multi-zone 1RIC model* is evaluated for the day 14/01/2005, considering time intervals of 5 minutes. Specifically, the parameters of the models are estimated using the proposed estimation framework presented in Section III-A considering the training period from 24/12/2004 to 13/01/2005. The day-ahead indoor temperature¹ for each zone of the four-zone building is predicted for the day 14/01/2005 using the estimated parameters of each model. Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) depict the daily electricity consumption in Zone 1 and outdoor temperature of the evaluation day used as input data in each model. For reproducible purposes, a description of the building, the EnergyPlus and weather files, and the parameters of all models are provided online in [18].

Fig. 4 illustrates the predicted indoor temperature obtained from the proposed *multi-zone 1RIC model* and *bimodal multi-zone 1RIC model* as well as the actual indoor temperature for Zone 1 for the evaluation day 14/01/2005. As shown in Fig. 4, the proposed *multi-zone 1RIC model* predicts well the daily indoor temperature of Zone 1, presenting a MAPE of 0.44% and MAE of 0.10°C (see Tables II and III). Fig. 4 also indicates the capability of the proposed *bimodal multi-zone*

¹To predict the day-ahead indoor temperature using the derived thermal models, we estimate the indoor temperature at time k using as input the estimated indoor temperature at time $k - 1$.

Fig. 3. Input data: (a) Electricity consumption of the radiant floor heating system in kW for Zone 1 and (b) outdoor environmental temperature in °C for the evaluation day 14/01/2005.

Fig. 4. The predicted daily indoor temperature (°C) obtained from the *multi-zone 1RIC model*, and *bimodal multi-zone 1RIC model* as well as the actual indoor temperature for Zone 1 for the evaluation day.

1RIC model to enhance the prediction accuracy by reducing the MAPE and MAE from 0.44% and 0.10°C to 0.16% and 0.04°C compared to the *multi-zone 1RIC model*. Note that the small temperature variation during the day (see Fig. 4) is due to the thermal inertia of the building and the radiant floor heating system that maintains the temperature in the range from 21°C to 23°C even when the heating system is *off*. Tables II and III present the MAPE and MAE, respectively, for the proposed thermal models for each zone of the building as well as their average values. As shown in Tables II and III, the Zones 1 – 3 present lower MAPE and MAE compared to Zone 4 due to their different thermostat operation (temperature set-point and limits). Tables II and III also show that the *bimodal multi-zone 1RIC model* reduces the average MAPE and MAE from 0.46% and 0.10°C to 0.21% and 0.05°C compared to the *multi-zone 1RIC model*, presenting an enhancement of 54.3% and 50%.

Aggregate Performance Evaluation. The prediction accuracy of the proposed *multi-zone 1RIC model* and *bimodal multi-zone 1RIC model* is evaluated and compared to the *single-zone 1RIC model* and *multi-zone 3R2C model* for the period 01/01/2005 - 30/01/2005 by calculating the MAPE and MAE of each day. To predict the indoor temperatures for each evaluation day, we train the four models using data from the previous 20 days. Note that the retraining of the models

TABLE IV
AVERAGE MAPE IN % FOR THE PERIOD 01/01/2005 - 30/01/2005.

Models	Zone 1	Zone 2	Zone 3	Zone 4	Average
Single-zone 1R1C	0.53%	0.40%	0.53%	1.06%	0.63%
Multi-zone 1R1C	0.45%	0.35%	0.42%	0.74%	0.49%
Bimodal 1R1C	0.19%	0.18%	0.20%	0.54%	0.28%
Multi-zone 3R2C	0.14%	0.13%	0.16%	0.19%	0.16%

TABLE V
AVERAGE MAE IN °C FOR THE PERIOD 01/01/2005 - 30/01/2005.

Models	Zone 1	Zone 2	Zone 3	Zone 4	Average
Single-zone 1R1C	0.12	0.09	0.12	0.23	0.14
Multi-zone 1R1C	0.10	0.08	0.09	0.16	0.11
Bimodal 1R1C	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.12	0.06
Multi-zone 3R2C	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.03

enhances their prediction accuracy because it captures the variation of the solar trajectory and the building orientation. Tables IV and V demonstrate the average MAPE and MAE, respectively, of the evaluation period for each zone as well as the total average for all zones. As shown in Tables IV and V, the *multi-zone 1R1C model* reduces the average MAPE and MAE from 0.63% and 0.14°C to 0.49% and 0.11°C compared to the *single-zone 1R1C model*, presenting an improvement of 22.2% and 21.4%. The tables also indicate the capability of the *bimodal multi-zone 1R1C model* to enhance the prediction accuracy by reducing the total average MAPE and MAE by 42.8% (from 0.49% to 0.28%) and 45.4% (from 0.11°C to 0.06°C) compared to *multi-zone 1R1C model*. As expected, the *multi-zone 3R2C model* yields the best performance because it considers the actual average surface temperature, reducing the MAPE and MAE from 0.28% and 0.06°C to 0.16% and 0.03°C, respectively. However, the surface temperature is unknown in practical applications.

Discussion. The *single-zone 1R1C model* and *multi-zone 1R1C model* can be easily integrated into MPC approaches using linear programming; however, the *multi-zone 1R1C model* is preferable because it improves the prediction accuracy compared to the *single-zone 1R1C model*. Although the high-order *multi-zone 3R2C model* yields the best performance considering as known the average surface temperature, it requires the measurement or prediction of the surface temperature. Note that the measurement or prediction of the average surface temperature requires extra sensors on each surface, i.e., walls and doors, which are often unavailable in practical applications. The *bimodal multi-zone 1R1C model* enhances the prediction accuracy compared to the *multi-zone 1R1C model* and yields a similar performance with the *multi-zone 3R2C model*, without necessitating the knowledge of the average surface temperature. Although the *bimodal multi-zone 1R1C model* results in MIP programs (when it is used in MPC frameworks) which are challenging to solve, they can be efficiently solved using state-of-the-art solvers.

V. CONCLUSION

This work develops a low-complexity *multi-zone 1R1C model* that captures the indoor temperatures of different zones in multi-zone buildings based on environmental conditions and

the energy consumption of their heating system. To enhance the prediction accuracy of the derived model, a *bimodal multi-zone 1R1C model* is proposed that considers individually the *on/off* states of the heating system. Moreover, an estimation framework is developed to estimate the parameters of both models using building data obtained from the EnergyPlus simulator and historical weather data. Simulation results show the ability of both models to predict well the daily indoor temperature in multi-zone buildings. The results also indicate the capability of the *bimodal multi-zone 1R1C model* to reduce the total average MAPE and MAE by 42.8% and 45.4% compared to the *multi-zone 1R1C model*. Future work will develop MPC frameworks to manage the indoor temperature and energy consumption of heating/cooling systems in multi-zone buildings by incorporating the proposed thermal models.

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